

Stability analysis of sea-cliffs coupling stress strain and hydrodynamic modelling: preliminary results from Punta Eolo case study (Ventotene, Italy)

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Summary

This research represents a preliminary attempt to couple hydrodynamic modelling of sea-related actions with stability analysis managed through a limit-equilibrium and stress-strain approaches to account for the action of sea waves on a sea cliff. The quantitative analysis revealed the possibility that instability conditions will be reached for specific rock blocks if the hydrostatic backpressure due to the rock cracks filling is combined with a pseudo-static force, genetically related to the elastic rebound caused by the sea wave slams. This condition is the most recurrent action at studied cliff of Punta Eolo in Ventotene (Italy). Finally, the project of the ongoing installation of a tailor-designed monitoring system is presented. The system will be used to characterize the physical nature of the sea-related preparatory and triggering factors on the cliff, and to examine the deformative response of the cliff itself under the action of periodic thermal and hydrodynamic stressors.

Introduction

Cultural heritage (CH) sites are often located in coastal areas affected by landslide activity (Spizzichino et al., 2013) potentially influenced by the effects of climate (Sesana et al., 2021). An increasing number of researchers has begun to turn their attention to the study of mitigation strategies for CH sites affected by landslides (e.g., Beni et al., 2023). Numerous researches focused on the study of coastal retreat processes (e.g., Alberti et al., 2022), however, limited are quantitative studies focused on the comprehension of the relationships existing between coastal landslide activity and the climate-related factors. In particular, is not yet fully understood the extent to which both preparatory and triggering climate-related factors can contribute to the control of the systems predisposed to host slope instabilities. This is the case of waves and wind, whose action is much studied in coastal engineering applications. In these terms, several well established modelling techniques can now quantify the extent of wave hydrodynamic effect on coastal structures, such as, bridges (Xiang & Istrati, 2021), piers (Hasanpour et al, 2021) and buildings (Hasanpour & Istrati, 2022), but they do not have been yet diffusively applied to natural systems. The Punta Eolo sea-cliff (Ventotene island, Italy) is here analysed since it is frequently affected by rock-falls and topples that are threatening the vulnerable remnants of the roman archaeological site of Villa Giulia. This latter is one of the pilot sites selected in the framework of the H2020 TRIQUETRA European project, aimed to proposing a methodological framework for mitigating climate-related natural hazards affecting cultural heritage.

Study area: the Punta Eolo sea cliff (Ventotene, Italy)

Ventotene is a volcanic island belonging to the Pontine Archipelago located offshore the Tyrrhenian coast between Rome and Naples. This island is of particular interest both for a naturalistic and historical point of view since it belongs to a natural park and because of the presence of several archaeological sites such as the one of the Villa Giulia. By a geological point of view, Ventotene Island, together with the smaller Santo Stefano Island, represent the tip of a large stratovolcano built during the last 800,000 years (Perrotta et al., 1996). The whole island is formed by a tuff plateau slightly dipping towards NE and bounded by active cliffs ranging from 10 to 130 meters of height (Caso et al., 2015). Many landslides struck all the boundaries of the island (Bosco et al., 2013) undermining the conservation of many archeological sites, including the one of Villa Giulia. This latter is located in the northernmost sector of the island (i.e., Punta Eolo promontory), where the youngest volcanic deposits are represented by tuff rocks, namely the Parata Grande Tuff (PGT) (Perrotta et al., 1996).

Engineering-geological model conceptualization and preliminary analysis of climate related factors acting on landslide's control

Direct and remote analyses were carried out to conceptualize the engineering geological model of the Punta Eolo cliff. Firstly, a geomechanical characterization of the PGT was conducted according to the ISRM (2007) standard. A 3D model of the cliff slope was also reconstructed by drone photogrammetry technique. This product provided a useful tool to *i*) extract the orientation of the not-directly detectable joints, and *ii*) measure the isolated rock-block dimensions. N. 60 single-station seismic noise measurements were carried out and were processed according to the Nakamura (1989) method. In this way it was possible to characterize the vibrational nature of the geological layering and to constrain the geological unit contacts. Finally, bathymetric profiles were reconstructed to account for the underwater interaction of sea-waves front approaching the analyzed cliff. The performed conceptualization revealed the predisposition of the Punta Eolo sea cliff to host rock-falls and topples landslide mechanisms according to the Markland (1972) kinematic analysis.

A preliminary analysis of the most efficient climate-related factors which stress the Ventotene Island was conducted to characterize both nature and entity of the preparatory and triggering factors that may contribute to the activation and evolution of the Punta Eolo sea cliff failures. The Ponza Station was selected as reference station since it is the closest to the Ventotene Island. The site is located about 40 km away the Punta Eolo cliff and it is represented by an offshore monitoring buoy belonging to the Italian data buoy network (Bencivenga et al., 2012).

Numerical modelling of sea-waves impact

For the hydrodynamic modelling of this study a mesh-based computational fluid dynamics (CFD) method that had been validated previously for extreme wave impact on coastal structures both in 2D and 3D conditions (Istrati & Buckle 2021) was utilized. In the preliminary analysis phase, three cross-sections (AA', BB', CC') were selected as shown in Figure 1. Moreover, the recorded data from the Ponza Station were analyzed and was found that the wave periods were between 2sec and 11.5sec, and the wave heights between 0.25m up to 6.8m. Using this information and the available bathymetries, high-fidelity two-dimensional models were developed for the selected cross-sections, which solved the Navier-Stokes equations with a Large Eddy Simulation (LES) turbulence model. This type of CFD model can capture the transient wave propagation and the most complex physical phenomena that include the

nonlinear transformation of the waves as they approach the coast and interact with the bathymetry (shoaling process), the reflection phenomenon, the wave breaking process and the wave-cliff interaction. Although the investigation is ongoing and the sensitivity of the results is being analysed, preliminary results are shown in Figure 1. Interestingly, the wave impact process seems to present different trends, with the wave breaking in some cases and causing violent phenomena and slamming, and in other cases just propagating smoothly over the slope of the cliff generating different hydrodynamic effects. This can be observed also in the force histories, which consists of both high impulsive peaks and longer-duration components. It is expected that the ongoing CFD analyses and careful post-processing of the data will help decipher the hydrodynamic effects in relation to the incoming wave conditions and the geometry of the cliff (cross-section).

Figure 1 Orthophoto with three selected cross-section (left) and example of results from preliminary CFD models including fluid velocities and horizontal forces on the cliff

Stability analysis of the Ventotene sea cliff

The slope stability conditions of sea cliff at Punta Eolo were evaluated for a rock-toppling mechanism and the slope stability analyses were performed under static and pseudo-static conditions following the methodology proposed by Martino & Mazzanti (2014). Both the seismic action and the static water pressure within the joint sets were analysed; in a second time of analysis, also the sea-wave action was considered as a force responsible for an elastic rebound (*sensu* Hutchinson, 1988). Thanks to the hydrodynamic modelling, it was possible to convert the maximum computed value for the acting force against the cliff related to the sea waves into a pseudo-static coefficient. This latter served as input for the factor of safety (FOS) calculation. A sensitivity analysis was carried out by changing the values of the triggering pseudo-static action, and stability charts were derived by considering a concurrent contribution of different pseudo-static actions (i.e., seismic and hydrostatic) to the FOS evaluation. A Preliminary stress-strain numerical model has been developed reproducing the role of joint interfaces. The performed pseudo-static analysis indicates that the stability conditions can be achieved in most of the detected rock-blocks for realistic triggering scenarios.

Conclusions

The performed pseudo-static analysis indicates that the stability conditions can be achieved in most of the detected rock-blocks for realistic triggering scenarios. The quantitative analysis revealed the possibility that unstable conditions will be reached for specific rock blocks if the

seismic action is combined with a hydrostatic backpressure, as well as in case that hydrostatic backpressure is combined with an elastic rebound caused by the sea wave pushing action. This latter condition is the most likely occurring at Punta Eolo in Ventotene; very high sea wave can in fact impact on the sea cliff as to surmount it, inducing the instantaneously filling of the tension cracks present behind the edge of the cliff. An integrated geophysical and geotechnical monitoring system is going to be designed at the Punta Eolo. At this aim, a suitable portion of the sea cliff was selected as representative for the local coastline. The installation will include several sensors that will be used to characterize the physical nature of the sea-related preparatory and triggering factors on the cliff, and to examine the deformative response of the cliff itself under the action of such stressors. The so recorded data will be used as an input for both the slope stability analysis and the hydrodynamic modelling of sea waves.

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